

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF FUTURE EDUCATORS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10323867>

Abstract. *Modern higher education is based on the student's ability to realize himself as a person and activate his inner strength to make independent choices, make decisions and take responsibility for them.*

In the article, the use of communication technologies in pedagogical higher education institutions highlights the creativity, improvement, self-awareness of the teacher, the activation of the professional growth of students, and the development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues.

Keywords: *skill, thinking, technology, interest, information, management, conclusion, activity.*

Higher education institutions should provide our society with creative thinking, high knowledge capacity, qualified specialists. For this, of course, attention should be paid to the level of professional training of pedagogues and engineer-pedagogues who provide education to young people.

The development of creative communicative abilities of future pedagogues to some extent indicates changes in the educational paradigm of higher education institutions, as a result of which education is presented as a method of knowing based on communicative forms of interaction between participants of the educational process, which provides new opportunities for the implementation of pedagogical tasks that determine the prospects for the development of education. includes

It should be noted that the traditional ideas about the development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues do not correspond to the new requirements of modern higher education based on the "subject-subject" relationship between teachers and students. Educational practice shows that teachers and students are not satisfied with the nature of interaction in the process of studying in a higher education institution. Teachers often have difficulties in establishing mutual communicative relations with students, because they do not know enough how to include them in joint activities at different stages of education, they do not know how to flexibly change the nature of interaction depending on changing conditions. Inadequate didactic provision of mutual communication with students leads teachers to give preference to monologue forms of education, and this leads to a decrease in the quality of training of future teachers in higher education institutions" [2].

It is necessary to deeply understand Sh.A. Amonashvili's ideas about the role of communication in human life: "In communication, people not only affect each other, not only exchange information, not only regulate mutual relations - but all these elements still do not

determine its essence. The conclusion is that through communication, people realize their humanity, individuality and uniqueness, that is, they live" [2].

B.F. Lomov said that through communication "a specific person owns a "fund of spiritual wealth" created by other people, as a result of which the limitations of his personal experience are overcome; at the same time, through communication, he brings what he has created to this "fund". This is what determines the importance of communication in a person's life" [8].

In other words, none of the human abilities can arise outside of communication. People around are primarily the only carriers that people can absorb. Secondly, interpersonal communication with people is necessary for a person to acquire this knowledge, skills and abilities. Thirdly, we are talking not only about interpersonal communication, but also about organizational, educational and developmental communication. Fourthly, the process of formation of knowledge, skills and competences should be monitored and evaluated, and this is done in direct communication with the persons who form these abilities.

Thus, a person is formed and develops in the process of interpersonal communication as a person in all its important aspects. According to GM Andreev, "People's communication with each other is more important in psychological development than activity. In communication with each other, tasks that are not available for one person are solved" [3]. Therefore, in our opinion, it is very important to determine the main characteristics of interpersonal communication, to develop creative communication skills of future pedagogues.

Pedagogical scientist S. In the research work of Matjonov, the issues of organization of oral and written creative works of students in classes were studied. After all, in the formation of a spiritually mature generation, creative works require free thinking. A student who does not have independent thinking, his own point of view cannot be creative, cannot work independently [9].

It is necessary to organize the development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues in the form of continuous creative research and direct them to a certain goal.

For this he:

- tend to manage the process of creative research;
- it should be remembered that the effectiveness of creative research depends on the pedagogical, psychological and theoretical preparation of the teacher.

It is known that in the process of education, students should form creative attitudes to learning, master the course materials at a high level.

There is a lack of desire for this, although today there are not enough teaching-methodical materials, textbooks and training manuals. Pedagogical scientist V.P. Bepalko paid attention to this issue and said, "If the textbook is composed indifferently to educational tasks, it is impossible to teach students to form their worldviews independently. If the educational goals of forming students' creative qualities and the directions for their achievement are not indicated in the textbooks, students will not be taught creative qualities, formation of abilities cannot be offered. On the other hand, students cannot be expected to master the lesson materials at a high-scientific level" [4].

In our opinion, the time has come when society and the educational system began to realize the role of interpersonal communication in human development, and this requires a rethinking of the modern education system. In this regard, as D.I. Dubrovsky noted, "Human transformation requires a high level of self-awareness. True self-knowledge is not only self-reflection, but also a creative factor that changes the value-content structure of consciousness, forms new goals of

activity, and serves as a generator of will and spiritual energy" [7]. But for these purposes, it is necessary to form a communicative type of thinking and provide a didactic solution to such a problem. Otherwise, a characteristic feature of educational reform ... is the impatience of reformers ... from education, the desire to introduce the concepts and teachings they propose as soon as possible into the technological and mass practice, even if these concepts are not theoretically based, but are tested by relevant local experience. may remain in the eternal stage [5].

The correct solution of the problem will depend on determining the age and individual characteristics of the students, as well as their unique personal characteristics, spirituality, educational level, pedagogical and professional maturity, etc. Conscious independence of students is formed in the order of application of acquired knowledge, skills and competences based on these motives - aspiration - interest - active conscious activity - the need for it [6].

The development of learning needs motivates the subject to be active and at the same time sets before him the task of acquiring knowledge and skills.

It is advisable to pay attention to the following in order to form students' learning skills:

- setting the specific goal of students' educational activities (exercises, independent work), achieving their understanding by students;
- to understand the work of each student and, at the same time, not to forget the work of the whole team;
- always develop students' ability to independently analyze their work, find the cause of mistakes and ways to eliminate and prevent them;
- not giving ready instructions for correcting mistakes, getting students to understand and find ways to eliminate these mistakes;
- always encourage creative approach of students depending on the performance of assignments;
- encouraging students to use new, advanced, high-performance work methods, helping them to understand emerging difficulties, creating conditions for their independent work;
- achieving to ensure students' creative approach to the educational process, conscious completion of assignments;
- providing regular support to students who are not able to learn well, for this, by repeating the work methods, encouraging them to carry out creative independent work;
- to monitor students' work at certain times, to give them relevant instructions and advice;
- creatively approaching the work process of the students, controlling and appropriately evaluating the independently performed work.

Currently, attention is paid to the fact that the development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues is an important factor in improving the quality of personnel training. In it, it is possible to make extensive use of problem conversation (conversation with the help of research questions) and create a basis for students to independently perform assignments and tasks without receiving ready-made instructions and recommendations.

In our case, the development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues should be designed to solve the existing contradiction between the teacher's training in science and his insufficient preparation for interpersonal communication in the educational process. Such specialists can be trained only in the conditions of communicative education, in subject-subject level systems.

By subject-subject interaction, we understand equal communication of partners (teachers and students) when there is an opportunity to express their personal "I" in the educational process. At the same time, in such a process, not only the scientific and cultural form of human interaction with the world is recreated, but also new elements are created. Both subjects are included in creative cognitive activities, within which subject, philosophical-methodological and professional competence of future students is formed.

Currently, it is known that "educational communication technology is one of the leading technologies of person-oriented education, and in recent years, the humanization and communicative orientation of education has brought interpersonal communication to the forefront" [10].

When using communication technologies, students acquire the ability to communicate at various levels, from informational to research. At the informational-problematic level, two types of communication are used: the teacher's thought communication (he creates problem situations, asks questions, puts forward hypotheses, but at the same time solves problems, answers questions) and internal communication of students, he reacts to the influence of the teacher with external behavior consists of being Only sometimes internal communication is broken by unplanned words. The activity of the teacher is effective at certain stages of such communication. This communication makes it possible to implement methods of obtaining new knowledge, to form methods of scientific activity such as analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparison, etc. The level of independence is not very high, but it is much higher than presenting the learning material in the form of a monologue.

At the strictly heuristic level, the teacher sets the task of involving students in direct participation in the implementation of a specific problem solving method in order to activate and increase their interest in knowledge. However, it basically uses the same content structure, but additionally uses informational questions that the students answer themselves. However, the management system used by the teacher is a strict guideline for the educational activities of students in the process of acquiring new knowledge. Acting according to the instructions, they gradually become familiar with the logic of building a thinking system that leads to certain conclusions or remember the sequence of practical actions that lead to the solution of a problem, which gradually forms the ability to plan their activities in solving further problems.

The use of this type of communication leads to the independence of students, because they participate in cognitive activities, but are under the strict control of the teacher.

At the free heuristic level, the teacher uses assignments and tasks during communication, in addition, at certain stages of heuristic communication. In contrast to strict heuristic communication, the teacher's instructions are not specific, but generalized ("think about how we should achieve the goal? What do we need to know to achieve it? How can we find intermediate unknowns? What should be used to find them?", etc.).

If we compare this communication with the previous one, it becomes clear that the independence of knowledge is at a higher level. They need to transfer previously known laws of action to new situations, analyze, compare, prove, justify, but now they can generalize, put forward hypotheses and choose the necessary tools. At the same time, the main aspect of this communication is that students demonstrate the ability to plan their activities at separate stages of problem solving.

At the research (research) level, research communication comes to the fore, assuming the independent solution of problem tasks. At the same time, this construction of educational material is used again and the elements of the heuristic communication structure are used, but now students plan their cognitive activities, perform them independently, the necessary scientific methods of cognitive activities and activities, reasoning, understanding the problem as a whole, self-control they consciously use the methods of doing and evaluating their own performance.

The research degree is the highest level of student independence. When such communication technologies are used, the following educational tasks are solved:

- 1) formation of critical and creative thinking of students;
- 2) development of the individual style of the future teacher's professional activity;
- 3) formation of necessary professional qualities of students to implement communicative education.

Development of creative communication skills of future pedagogues is not only a form of communication between people, but also a modern educational method.

In the field of modern higher education, education is directed to the personal sphere of students, and in this context, communicative education is the main component based on the student's ability to realize himself as a person and activate his inner forces to make independent choices, make decisions and take responsibility for them.

Conclusion

"The use of communication technologies in pedagogical higher educational institutions activates the teacher for creativity, improvement, self-awareness, professional growth, helps to form communicative skills, speed of thinking and flexibility in decision-making, which leads to better training of future teachers in higher educational institutions" [1].

We highlight the following necessary elements of any communication technology:

- planning and setting goals;
- goal motivation and strict orientation to the implementation of the entire direction of interpersonal relations;
- achievement of guaranteed educational goals;
- control and self-control, evaluation of results and self-evaluation.

Pedagogical communication technology should perform the following tasks in the formation of new concepts in students:

- cognitive (science, philosophical-methodological, professional). Concerning knowledge and how to acquire it;
- competent-active (science, philosophical-methodological, professional). It is related to the process of formation of skills based on the acquisition of knowledge and the ways of putting these skills into practice;
- creative (science, philosophical-methodological, professional). It is related to the creative illumination of the possibilities of communication participants;
- reflexive (science, philosophical-methodological, professional). It is related to the awareness of science, philosophical-methodological, professional activity in the educational process;
- motivational-valued (science, philosophical-methodological, professional). It is related to the motives and attitudes of a person and is manifested in the process of realizing his competence.

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